

BEYOND ETHNICITY: LIVED EXPERIENCES OF MATHEMATICS TEACHERS TEACHING IN RECOGNIZED INDIGENOUS PEOPLES SCHOOLS

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Beyond Ethnicity: Lived Experiences of Mathematics Teachers Teaching in Recognized Indigenous Peoples Schools

Ella Mae M. Lopez*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

It can be acknowledged that IPED educators may have distinct experiences being assigned to far-flung IP communities. An interest in exploring the real-world experiences of mathematics teachers teaching in IP-implementing schools, their coping strategies, and insights they may share with the community have been sparked. A qualitative-phenomenological design was employed to examine and delve into the procedure and connection of the experiences experienced by mathematics teachers at IPED-recognized schools. The extracted narratives were further examined through thematic analysis. The themes for the lived experiences were as follows: language barrier; difficulty in teaching mathematical concepts; establishing a teacher-student connection; learning culture and beliefs; lack of technology; struggling against student comprehension; alienation; challenge on perceived unsuitability of learning materials; and disrespect from the student. Meanwhile, the themes drawn for coping strategies are as follows: adaptation, language learning of teachers, help-seeking behavior, implementation of peer learning, and implementation of learner-centered instruction. Lastly, the themes regarding the shared insights to the academe and community are passion for teaching, companionship, and personal and professional growth.

Keywords: *education, mathematics, IPED schools, elementary public school teachers, phenomenology, Philippines*

Introduction

Some teachers are assigned to Indigenous Peoples (IP) schools who do not share the same ethnic background as the local community. Most Indigenous people's education teachers are significantly challenged by various pedagogical issues, lack of resources, and orientation of students and the community (Saysi & Batuctoc, 2022). Additionally, these teachers often encounter difficulties reaching and leaving the schools as they are usually labeled as geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas (Oxtero, 2022). Further, some of these challenges are the explanation of mathematical misconceptions (Karali, 2022), communicating mathematical processes (Lavidas et al., 2022), and providing positive reinforcement to change the negative attitude of students towards mathematics (Mojica, 2019).

Consequently, Indigenous people learners often need help understanding their lessons and are unsatisfied with their performance (Buenafior, 2023). Further, the study by Sicat and David (2016) revealed that IP grade school learners have low performance in mathematics, with 50.98 percent in computational skills, and below average in problem-solving, with 29.49 percent. Similarly, the current generation of Filipino students is revealed to have better foundational mathematics skills (Igarashi & Suryadarma, 2023). This phenomenon is often seen as the accountability of the teachers (Ama, 2019).

Experiences are crucial in our daily lives, particularly in teaching. Teachers assigned in IP schools have unique approaches to incorporating their lived experiences into teaching mathematics to their Indigenous learners. However, Abina and Evardo Jr (2024) elucidated that many developed countries have implemented Indigenous education programs like Inuit, and Métis education programs in Canada (Greenwood et al., 2020), Kaupapa Māori in New Zealand (Pihama, 2019), Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Education in Australia (Price & Rogers, 2019), the Indian Education Act and the Johnson-O'Malley Act in the United States (Marcus & Zens, 2023), and Sámi Education in Norway (Keskitalo, 2019). In Asia, such programs encompass Tribal Education in India (Velusamy, 2021), the Orang Asli Education Programme in Malaysia (Rosnon, 2016), and the Education Act for Indigenous Peoples in Taiwan (Ministry of Education, 2020). Hence, integrating Indigenous education can improve teaching methods and positively impact student learning (Battiste, 2013).

In Chicago, Indigenous teachers or those with extensive understanding of Indigenous cultures reveal the exposure of Indigenous communities (Castagno & Brayboy, 2008). Hence, there is a challenge in building relationships with the community, especially with their elders, and also considering their history. In contrast, the educators forbade them from practicing their culture and traditions (Roy et al., 2016). Meanwhile, there is also a high turnover rate among teachers teaching in Indigenous communities in Australia due to the instabilities they experienced in the remote localities (Hall, 2012).

As for Thailand, the movement to resist the erasure of the statehood of IP communities is being led through education, which puts additional challenges among the educators in these localities (Leepreecha & Meixi, 2019). Furthermore, mathematics education faces several challenges, such as a shortage of well-qualified teachers to teach IPs and insufficient expertise in curriculum development, textbook writing, and teaching methodologies (Roath, 2012). Many teachers lack proper training and experience, and classrooms often have a high student-teacher ratio.

These problems are making it difficult for teachers to teach mathematics. As to the study of Kaur and Noman (2015), teachers are

essential in recognizing cultural diversity in their classrooms, integrate their own cultural backgrounds, beliefs, experiences, and attitudes into their teaching and the development of educational strategies. Accordingly, Panthi and Belbase (2017) argued that educators often implement Western mathematics curriculum without considering the needs of students, the diversity and values of society, or the customs of Eastern cultures.

In the Philippines, various initiatives, such as integrating cultural heritage in lessons, have been introduced to enhance the quality of education for Indigenous communities. Hence, these efforts aim to make education more inclusive and culturally relevant, ensuring that Indigenous students receive an education that respects and integrates their cultural norms and backgrounds (Tancontian et al., 2024). Additionally, teachers often lack adequate preparation to teach Indigenous students effectively and are not provided with the necessary resources to help these students develop their abilities and skills (OECD, 2017). Further, continuous pursuits to enhance the undertakings of educators in the country in the context of IP culture are being mandated, which further fosters implications of the IPED (Arzadon, 2020).

Meanwhile, numerous recognitions were given to the municipality of Malita in the Davao Region, such as the IP School of Kyasan and the IP School of LebLeb, which gained acknowledgment for their efforts in providing education tailored to indigenous communities. However, these schools face challenges, including lack of culturally appropriate learning resources and teachers who lack expertise in indigenizing lessons. Hence, these challenges hinder the effectiveness of the Indigenous Peoples Education (IPED) Program (De Vera, 2024).

Furthermore, Lariosa et al. (2022) mentioned that many teachers in Indigenous Peoples (IP) schools continuously advocate for providing decent education in remote areas despite receiving little attention in the broader educational system of a particular province. With that being said, teachers in these remote IP schools take professional chances and use their perspectives and values to help students find peace, confidence, and fulfillment without fear, dissatisfaction, pressure, or despair. Moreover, their unique journey in the teaching profession offers a viable opportunity to explore significant and innovative teaching methods.

Notably, an IP teacher's teaching at IPED-implementing schools is not widely explored by scholars. However, the concept of workplace belongingness has been explored by some researchers (Hau, 2023), which shows that having the same culture and beliefs can result in a faster sense of belongingness and building relationships with other stakeholders. However, some studies highly focus on the lived experiences of the IP learners (Flores, 2014), the relationship of teachers and classroom management (No et al., 2022), and English teachers (Tagudando, 2022). Other studies have focused on the international scenario but are limited to the local set-up. Social issues such as peer relationships (Stark et al., 2015), school features (Shin, 2012), and social ties (Matlasz et al., 2020) have been the focus of previous cross-ethnic studies.

Nevertheless, issues about academic attainment have received scant attention in previous cross-ethnic research. There are frequently noticeable ethnic disparities in academic achievement. Thus, there is a need for studies focused on mathematics teachers, especially in elementary education among IP-implementing schools. Along this line, I was inspired to conduct a study focusing on the lived experiences of mathematics teachers teaching at IPED-implementing schools. The conduct of the study may potentially fill the literature gap and studies exploring the participant's lived experiences. Also, as Filipino students' low mathematics performance has been revealed while teaching mathematics among IP students, they also have their respective challenges. This study may provide additional insights into this persistent challenge.

The conduct of the study can be perceived to be aligned and can potentially contribute to the national program called AmBisyon Natin 2040, which aims to provide every Filipino a stable and comfortable quality of life, where education was one of the deemed pillars to achieve it (NEDA, 2016). The project also centers on the investment in education to enhance educational outcomes (Uy, 2023). Thus, IPs are also included in this vision, and conducting a study that explores the education system among the IPED-implementing schools through their teachers may also contribute to this program. Ultimately, it shows that while IPs are still recognized as marginalized during the study, their conduct may contribute to alleviating life conditions among these individuals through education.

To delve into the real-world experiences of mathematics teachers teaching in IP-implementing schools, I intend to share the findings in our School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions. This presentation will facilitate discussions on potential strategies for implementing the identified framework. I am also open to presenting this study at our District Research Forum to raise awareness among teachers, school heads, and instructional leaders, encouraging efforts to enhance the educational system.

Further, I will present this study during the Barangay Session with the elders of the Indigenous People in the community. This aims to raise awareness and foster collaboration towards achieving the common objective of enhancing the academic performance of Indigenous Peoples learners. Likewise, upon approval, I plan to publish the research study in local, national, and international journals. This publication will also contribute as supplementary literature for subsequent research endeavors.

Research Questions

My aim of this study was to explore and understand the lived experiences of teachers teaching mathematics among recognized Indigenous Peoples schools in a chosen districts Malita, Davao Occidental. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of mathematics teachers in recognized Indigenous Peoples schools?

2. How do the participants cope with the challenges in teaching mathematics in recognized Indigenous Peoples schools?
3. What insights can be shared with the academe and the community?

Methodology

Participants

The 17 mathematics teachers from IP-recognized schools in selected districts of Malita, Davao Occidental, were chosen for this study and met the specific criteria for this research. At least seven teachers participated in the in-depth interview (IDI), and ten teachers participated in the focus group discussion (FGD). There were two school districts in the Municipality of Malita, and I chose two schools from these districts. The participant sample size complied with the guidelines for performing IDI and FGD in a qualitative study, particularly in a phenomenological investigation. According to Creswell (2013), a sample size of three to ten cases is appropriate to obtain data saturation of variability and understand the respondents' lived experiences. This can be supported by (Vasileiou et al., 2018), who mentioned that such a sample size is enough for interviews.

Purposive or selective sampling was used in the synthesis to get a tolerable amount of data (Ames et al., 2019). Participants were selected based on their willingness to discuss their experiences with the phenomenon. Further, the selected participants were individuals able to provide more effective responses to the research questions and enhance their understanding of the phenomenon being investigated. In this case, as a sort of non-probability sampling, where researchers use their discretion to choose members of the population to participate in their study, Foley (2018) contends that purposive sampling is suitable. The qualities of the sample criteria are also necessary for someone to belong to the target population. The teachers must be mathematics teachers employed in an IP-recognized school for this study to be reliable. Specifically, preference was given to teachers with a minimum of one year of experience in either of the selected schools catering to IP learners.

This was done to ensure the teachers understand and have the necessary field experience. The participants have to be teachers teaching mathematics subjects in IP-recognized schools. They can be of any age, gender, or race if they meet the inclusion criteria. Some schools that implemented the IP program were situated in remote areas that were challenging to access. Consequently, the availability of reliable internet connections for participants was also considered, ensuring smooth online IDI and FGD. The participant's commitment and willingness were recognized to allocate time amid their hectic schedules to share their experiences related to the study. For the exclusion criteria, teachers who are IPs and are not teaching mathematics in an IP-recognized school were excluded from the participant selection.

Procedure

Following its approval, the researcher forwarded the letter to the panel of experts for validation, where they tediously checked the research instrument to ensure its reliability and validity. After validating the questionnaires, I distributed the Informed Consent Form (ICF) to participants chosen explicitly for the IDI and FGD, aiming to obtain their written consent as willing participants in the study. Then, I arranged the IDI and focus FGD at a time that suited the participants best. Additionally, I informed them in the ICF that the interview sessions were recorded to ensure that no essential information was overlooked.

Since some of the selected schools are located in rural areas without access to reliable signal, I visited the community for the in-person interview while making sure to adhere to COVID-19 pandemic protocols like social distancing and wearing masks even though the pandemic has ended to ensure that the participants, as well as myself, were safe. Meanwhile, I conducted an online IDI and FGD for the participants who had access to reliable signals even if they were situated in rural areas using the messenger and Zoom programs. After the interview, I transcribed the notes, and I asked the participants to review them for accuracy. The participants could add, remove, or make any other modifications they like.

Moreover, the information provided by all participants was kept confidential, and no individual was identified by their name during or after the research project. Instead, I used the codes for identification purposes. I secured all electronic data on a private computer with password protection, and an external hard drive was also employed with password protection.

Ethical Considerations

To address ethical concerns in my research, the study underwent a thorough evaluation by the Research Ethics Committee at the University of the Immaculate Conception (UIC – REC) prior to initiation. I followed the complete ethical standards in the conduct of the study, particularly in managing the population and data, including but not limited to:

Social Value. As a researcher, I aimed for this study to enhance the existing body of knowledge, mainly focusing on IP-implementing schools in the Philippines. This involved documenting the actual experiences of teachers and the difficulties they have faced. The insights from the research can be valuable for teachers and school administrators in enhancing the execution of IP education. I intend to disseminate the findings through webinars, research forums, and reputable international and national academic journals. Additionally, I have plans to publish this research in a reputable journal.

Informed Consent. In ethical research, informed consent is the fundamental principle (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). It entails ensuring that participants are provided with comprehensive information regarding the tasks they undertook, the purpose and utilization of the

collected data, and any potential outcomes or repercussions. The participants were given the choice to engage without penalty or consequence. They were informed and let them understand the purpose and benefits of the study; their rights to participate were carefully examined and respected. This study involved teachers as participants who are of legal age and capable of making their own decisions.

Before initiating the IDI and FGD, I planned to submit a formal request letter to the principals and school heads of the selected schools, seeking permission to conduct the research study. Upon obtaining approval, I sought explicit permission from the participants to engage in the IDI and FGD. I ensured the acquisition of both verbal and written consent from the participants and facilitated signing consent forms through email and various online platforms. The Informed Consent Form (ICF) showed the participants' agreement.

Vulnerability of the Participants. A vulnerable participant refers to any person who does not possess the capacity to give complete consent for their involvement in a study. Given that this study centers on adult teachers with the autonomy to make their own decisions, I provided informed consent forms to potential participants before conducting the FGD and IDI. I took measures to guarantee confidentiality in this regard, assuring that the organizations they belong to remained unidentified and their names were not disclosed in the study. Their responses were treated as confidential information. Therefore, in this research investigation, I prioritized safeguarding the integrity of my participants' wisdom and knowledge by approaching the entire process with sensitivity.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. Maintaining the confidentiality or anonymity of participants is crucial, and the measures taken should go beyond simply safeguarding their names. It is essential to avoid disclosing self-identifying statements or information that could reveal their identity (Fleming & Zegwaard, 2018). I followed protocols to ensure the respondents' information's safety and privacy and minimize risks and discomforts. I faced a potential risk related to protecting confidentiality and privacy during my research. I reassured the participants that their identities will remain undisclosed. To maintain confidentiality, I took measures such as safeguarding their names and securely storing all the data obtained from the interviews. I also shared the study's results with the participants. I encouraged participants to seek clarification by asking questions. The guide questions employed in this study were inherently non-offensive. Also, to ensure the health and safety of the participants, I wore a facemask during the interview, and some participants may be interviewed remotely using Zoom or messenger applications.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The respondent's personal and professional information that may be required in the study were kept private, and the respondents' data were kept as confidential as possible. I followed the guidelines in the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which emphasized the importance of transparency, using personal information for valid reasons, and ensuring that such information collection, storage, and handling is appropriate and proportional. The information was securely stored in a locked cabinet, and the tapes were disposed of once the study was finished to ensure the safety of the data (Burns & Grove, 2001).

Justice. As a researcher, I ensured that all respondents would be treated equally and fairly. The analysis of the results was impartial and objective, devoid of any personal prejudice or judgments. Additionally, I arranged in-person and virtual interviews and group discussions (IDI and FGD) at a convenient time for the participants, considering their busy schedules. Moreover, I was mindful of the duration of these sessions, recognizing the value of their time.

Transparency. The study results were objectively interpreted to serve its aim. I ensured that no personal interests were involved in the design of this study. Furthermore, the researcher's goal to discover, improve, and raise awareness motivated this research work, not monetary gain or recognition. I allowed my participants to review the transcripts of their interviews to ensure the accuracy of the information they shared. It is essential to acknowledge and attribute knowledge or information obtained from external sources by crediting the authors and specifying the sources of the ideas. Additionally, I validated the study with the participants before publishing it and gave them the final research output.

Qualification of the Researcher. As an elementary public-school teacher in an IP-implementing school and the IPED Program coordinator for over two years, my professional background inspired me to conduct this research. The inspiration behind this study were my colleagues and a genuine curiosity about how they navigated the obstacles associated with teaching IP learners. I am a student pursuing a Master of Arts degree in Education specializing in Mathematics. The research also adhered to the ethical guidelines set by the University of the Immaculate Conception Research Ethics Committee. Furthermore, I received guidance from my thesis adviser, panelists, and the Research Ethics Committee at the University of the Immaculate Conception.

Adequacy of Facilities. The sufficiency of the existing resources indicates how suitable the exposure and knowledge accessible to candidates can be (Oladokun & Ayodele, 2015). As a researcher, I ensured that all the facilities for this study were adequate and available. Therefore, the UIC, where I am enrolled, has granted graduate students the convenience of remotely accessing library resources and online materials from ProQuest, IG Library, ERIC, and PH EJournal, which have contributed significantly to the completion of this study. Furthermore, I possessed my own internet connection, recorder, and laptop, which have been crucial resources for me to pursue my academic endeavors. Moreover, I have had the opportunity to consult with a skilled team of experts in the research field when guidance is required.

Community Involvement. The study involved the participation of the people in the community. I assured that the study supports and improves the problem seen in the community. As a researcher, I am committed to honoring the community of public-school teachers and their lived experiences in teaching in an IP-implementing school. I hold high regard for the perspectives of the participants. The

study findings will be shared with school heads, principals, and their respective teachers. Another approach to engaging the community is showcasing this paper at research conferences held locally, nationally, and internationally. As a researcher, it is my duty and commitment to share the results of my research with the public, thereby contributing to the existing knowledge in the field.

Results and Discussion

This section of the paper presents the research findings, which were gathered and analyzed through an appropriate data analysis tool. Specifically, this chapter presents the data sufficing the lived experiences of mathematics teachers in recognized Indigenous people schools, how participants cope with the challenges in teaching mathematics in recognized Indigenous people schools, and insights shared with the academe and community.

Profile of the Participants

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the teachers at IP-recognized schools. Specifically, 41.18 percent of the participants participated in the in-depth interview, while 58.82 percent participated in the focus group discussions. Moreover, 70.59 percent of the female participants dominated the sample size, considering that there were only five male participants or 29.41 percent of the sample size. As illustrated, the youngest participant was FGD9, 24 years old, while the oldest was FGD6, 38 years old. Further, the participants with the shortest rendered service were IDI1 and FGD9, who had one year each, while the one with the longest rendered service of 11 years was FGD1. Lastly, the most prominent ethnicity of the teachers was Bisaya, which comprises 70.59 percent of the sample size.

Table 1.1. *Demographic Profile of Participants*

Code	Sex	Age	Years in Service	Study Group	Ethnicity
IDI1	Female	29	1	IDI	Bisaya
IDI2	Male	30	7	IDI	Bisaya
IDI3	Male	36	3	IDI	Cebuana
IDI4	Female	26	3	IDI	Tagakaolo
IDI5	Female	25	2	IDI	Bisaya
IDI6	Male	25	2	IDI	Bisaya
IDI7	Male	31	7	IDI	Manobo
FGD1	Female	37	11	FGD	Bisaya
FGD2	Female	31	3	FGD	Tagakaolo
FGD3	Female	31	10	FGD	Bisaya
FGD4	Male	34	3	FGD	Tagakaolo
FGD5	Female	29	2	FDG	Bisaya
FGD6	Female	38	2	FGD	Bisaya
FGD7	Female	26	3	FGD	Bisaya
FGD8	Female	27	5	FGD	Bisaya
FGD9	Female	24	1	FGD	Bisaya
FGD10	Female	30	6	FGD	Bisaya

Lived Experiences of Mathematics Teachers in Recognized Indigenous Peoples Schools

The following themes, which I categorized, were derived from the lived experiences of mathematics teachers among recognized IP schools.

Table 1.2. *Lived Experiences of Mathematics Teachers in Recognized Indigenous Peoples Schools*

Essential Themes	Core Ideas
Language Barrier	Struggles of teachers in communicating Difficulty explaining among students with different language The difference of utilized language as barrier for learning
Difficulty in Teaching Mathematics	Lack of equivalent term of mathematical concepts in indigenous language Weak foundation for mathematics among IP learners Difficulty with complex mathematical lessons for elementary
Establishing Teacher-Student Connection	Problems on connecting with students due to communication concerns Emotional factor of students and teachers in the teaching and learning process The problem with the language difference in bridging in the classroom context
Learning Culture and Beliefs	Cultural differences among teachers and the community Learning styles and preferences using cultural lens Adapting with the environment
Lack of Technology	No internet access Lack of technological assistance for learning Technology as potential bridge for seeing the world
Struggling Against Student Comprehension	Low Lesson Retention Low student engagement due to minimal comprehension of lessons The learning curve of IP learners

Alienation	Feeling of being in a foreign land Unmatched ethnicity Perception on indigenous language as foreign language
Challenge in Perceived Unsuitability of Learning Materials	Demand for more suitable learning resources Struggles to comprehend language used for textbooks Request for appropriate and effective translations
Disrespect from Students	Perceived disrespect through classroom behavior of students Usage of indigenous language to disrespect teachers Received insulting laughter

Language Barrier. The teachers have experienced struggles in communicating and explaining mathematical concepts to learners with different dialects. They did not know the native language commonly used by the learners. Exploring their experiences as an IPED teacher revealed that they struggled to impart their knowledge, which impacted the delivery of the lesson. The following utterances of the participants can further describe this:

It was difficult to teach math because I didn't know their language yet... - (IDI3)

...struggle jud sya kay dili man gud mi parahas ug dialect na ginagamit. So for example, ang number 1 sa ato a kay one or isa, ilaha didto lahi ang 1 sa ilaha didto... - (IDI4)

I struggle because we don't use the same dialect. So for example, the way we say number 1 is different from them.

...language lang man jud ang ... pinaka lisod jud... unsaon nimo pag communicate sa imong nabal an kung dili ka kabalo sa ilang language. - (IDI6)

Language is the most difficult there. How will you communicate or share your thoughts if you don't know their language.

...naa jud syay language barrier kay dili jud nimo ma explain tanan gusto nimo ma iingon regarding sa topic ba kay naay uban ... kaayo kasabot ug bisaya. - (FGD5)

There is a language barrier because you can't explain all the things you wanted to say regarding the topic because there ... who can't understand bisaya.

Difficulty in Teaching Mathematical Concepts. The teachers had met the challenges in teaching mathematical concepts since there were no equivalent terms in indigenous language. In addition, IP learners had a poor foundation in mathematics and very complex mathematical lessons, which contributed to the difficulty of the teachers in teaching mathematical concepts. Further, the following utterances can describe this theme:

Example kanang dili kayo sila kabalo sa tagalog word pag mag...like sa symbols, division and then sa katong ... fraction. - (IDI1)

Example is that they don't know tagalog word that much like the symbols, division and then in fraction.

...ang kanang ilang foundation gud sa math kay dili kaayo ing ana ka strong... ilang level kay dili pajud kaayo pang grade 3, mag lisod pajud. - (IDI5)

Their foundation in math is not strong enough, their level is not enough for a grade 3 student, they still struggle.

...basic operations, diba naa manay mga fraction, decimals... so pag abot na diha nga part medyo diha na jud mag sugod ang ginaingon nga difficulty... - (IDI6)

In basic operation, there is fraction, decimals. In that part, it is where difficulty start.

Yes, lisod jud sya. For example, is kanang mag pasabot ka sa ilaha sa mga mathematical word... - (FGD3)

Yes, it is difficult. For example, when you explain to them the mathematical words.

Establishing Teacher-Student Connection. Another theme that emerged from the participants' lived experiences focused on establishing a connection with the IP students. The teachers struggled to connect with their learners because the teacher could not understand or speak the learners' language, which affected the learners' eagerness to learn. Despite the challenge of language differences, the teachers remained committed and tried their best to teach the learners with excitement and enthusiasm to build a strong connection with the learners. Specifically, the following utterances expound this theme:

...I cannot easily connect and elaborate the lessons well, and they did not immediately understand what I was saying. - (IDI3)

...luoy pud jud baya ang mga bata... maong... ma excite jud ko mag tudlo kay masking dili kaayo ko kabalo sa ilahang language at least maka tabang japon ko sa ilaha. - (IDI5)

I pity the children, so whenever it is math time, I am excited to teach them even though I don't know their language that much at least I can still help them.

...ug same mi ug kuan... ug language edi syempre... so kanang murag maka affect sya ba nga mahimong eager ang bata nga maka learn. – (FGD4)

If we have the same language, I think it can affect the eagerness of the students to learn.

Learning Culture and Beliefs. Learning about a specific community's culture and beliefs can help build a stronger connection with the people and learn more about them. In line with this, learning the culture of the learners provided the teachers with valuable insights into their learning styles and preferences. This cultural awareness of the teachers enabled them to tailor their teaching methods to be more effective and better suit the needs of the learners. Further, the following utterances from the participants may describe the theme:

...learn and know the other peoples culture, beliefs, and unsa pa... kay dili man pari pariha ang tao ug tinuohan ug language. – (IDI1)

Learn and know the other peoples culture, and beliefs because people don't have the same beliefs and language.

...naa koy na learn sa ilahang culture ug language... ug kanang kuan... naa koy nahibal an about sa ilang learning styles ug preferences... – (IDI5)

I have learned something in their culture and language, and also in their learning styles and preferences.

...shocking kung baga... kanang ang... culture man gud lahi, ang approach lahi, ang communication lahi, so mag lisod jud kag teach sa ilaha... struggle sya... – (IDI6)

It was shocking, it's because the culture, approach, and communication are different, so it is difficult to teach them, the struggle is there.

...dapat flexible ka kung asa gani ka ma assign dapat jud ta mag adapt sa ilahang language or culture, tun an jud ... imong pag tudlo sa ilaha... – (FGD4)

You have to be flexible wherever you are assign, you have to learn and adapt in their language and culture in order for you to teach them easily.

Lack of Technology. This theme focuses on the need for teachers to experience more technology as they strived to undertake their duty to provide education at their respective locations. Technology helps teachers improve their learning of mathematics. Learning with technology has provided access to a wide range of educational resources, allowing learners to explore and understand the different parts of the world. This exposure enhanced their knowledge, especially in mathematics. The utterances of the participants further describe this theme:

...no access to technology and internet. Need jud baya ang math sa pang adlaw adlaw nuh labi na didto sa bukid. – (IDI5)

No access to technology and internet. Math is essential in daily live especially in the mountain.

...need more assistance to enhance learning like putting technology site para maka search ug maka learn sila ug new things from different areas.– (FGD10)

Needs more assistance to enhance learning like putting technology site in order for them to search and learn new things from different areas.

Struggling Against Student Comprehension. The academic gap of the learners in the mountains are different, they tend to forget lessons quickly. The learners' comprehension of the lesson affected their engagement in the discussion, as it was closely linked to their learning curves. Consequently, teachers tried to simplify the lessons to enhance the learners' comprehension. Further, the theme can be described by their utterances:

...pag itudlo nimo karon, pagka ugma malimtan na dayon nila, unya dili kayo sila kabalo sa two words, ang ilaha lang kay isa isa... Dili kaayo nila ma digest ang topic. – (IDI1)

What you teach today, they will forget it tomorrow. They don't know two words or two digits well. They can't digest the topic very well.

...kanang mag basa lang ka sa ilaha, kanang maminaw lang sila, kay dili man gud sila ka sabot ana. – (IDI4)

When you just read for them, and then they will just listen because they can't understand in that way.

...lahi ilang academic gap ba...dugay sila maka sabot... – (IDI5)

Their academic gap is different, they can't understand easily.

...mas grabe jud ilahang learning curve considering nga layo kaayo silag gigikanan tapos...dili sila physically and mentally prepared ba sa pagsulod. – (IDI6)

Their learning curve is extreme considering the place they came from then when they arrive at school, they are not physically and

mentally prepared.

...dapat naa jud silay makita kaysa isulat ra. Kay ang uban bata loading pa baya kaayo. – (FGD6)

There should be something they can see instead of just writing because some learners can't understand easily.

Alienation. Teachers felt like they were in a different country because they could not understand the language in the community. Belonging to a community with different ethnicities evoked a sense of novelty and unfamiliarity within that community. In line with this, the following utterances can describe it:

Mura kog naa sa laing nasod, kay same raman ang feeling na dili mi magka sinabot. – (IDI4)

It feels like I am in a different country because I can't understand them.

...amoa man gud na assignan nga school is dili sya tugma sa akoang ethnicity...mura syag foreign language. – (FGD4)

The community of the school where I was assigned doesn't have the same ethnicity with the one that I have, the language is like a foreign language.

Challenge on Perceived Unsuitability of Learning Materials. This theme establishes the findings regarding the unsuitable learning materials provided among the participants for learning delivery. Learning materials became more engaging and effective when linked to the culture and language of the specific community. Providing learning materials translated into the learners' language can significantly improve their understanding of the lesson and create a more effective learning environment. Specifically, the following utterances provide a description:

Unya ang libro siguro... or ang gigamit nga libro nga gamiton dapat kuan siguro... dapat kanang medyo tagakaulo gyud with halong bisaya...

– (IDI2)

The book should have been at least translated in tagakaulo mixed with bisaya.

...kanang copy sa mga resources nga murag translation gud sya from bisaya to b'laan, kanang murag dictionary. – (FGD4)

The copy of the resources like translation of words from bisaya to b'laan, something similar with the dictionary.

Disrespect from Students. This theme focuses on the participants' lived experiences regarding the disrespect they have received from the students. Teachers felt disrespected when learners spoke in their language and laughed while the teacher was present. Such actions could lead teachers to wonder whether they were the subject of the laughter due to their inability to understand the language. The following utterances may further describe this:

...nag storya siya sa iyang dialect... wala man pud ko kasabot...naay niduol sa akua nga student...nako unya ana sya nga lain daw to ang buot pasabot sa gistorya atong bata... – (IDI4)

The student is talking using their language and I don't understand it but one of my students said that what the other student said was not good.

...ginakataw an ko nila, kay usahay akong ginagamit nga bisaya word kay lahi na diay ug meaning sa ilaha... – (IDI6)

They laughed at me, because sometimes the bisaya word I used have different meaning in their language.

...ang uban student baya mag hinunghungay unya mangatawa...tapos ikaw nga dili maka sabot sa ilang ... ka ba nga basi ikaw ang gi storyahan – (FGD6)

Some students whispered something to each other and then they laugh, and as for you who can't understand them ... the one they are talking to.

Based on the details provided above, those categories were crucial areas where challenges related to the lived experiences of mathematics teachers in recognized Indigenous peoples' schools were highlighted. As indicated, language plays a crucial role in the teaching learning process as experienced among educators, especially those teaching mathematics in IP-recognized schools. The experiences of the educators were mainly anchored in the struggles experienced by individuals who were natives in the locale, where the culture and language were different from theirs. Additionally, the experiences illustrated the challenges related to the remote locality, which entails the lack of access to the technology.

Coping Strategies of the Participants

I categorized and labeled the themes derived from the participants' narratives regarding the coping strategies in teaching among the recognized Indigenous Peoples schools in Davao Occidental and transcribed IDI and FGD. Specifically, Table 2 shows the themes drawn for this section: adaptation, language learning of teachers, help-seeking behavior, implementation of peer learning, and

implementation of learner-centered instruction.

Table 2. *Coping Strategies of Participants in Teaching Mathematics in Recognized Indigenous Peoples Schools*

<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Adaptation	Leveling to the needs and capabilities of IP learners Culture adjustments of teachers
Language Learning of Teachers	Gradual learning and adjustment to the IP culture Striving to learn the local dialect Language as crucial part of communication Learning language for teaching process
Help-Seeking Behavior	Seeking assistance from co-teachers Seeking assistance from parents of learners Leveraging home-visits for seeking assistance for language learning
Implementation of Peer-Learning	Strategic group activities Peer-to-peer learning among IP learners
Implementation of Learner-Centered Instruction	Creation of manipulatives for effective teaching The need for visual resources Innovative teaching

Adaptation. The first theme for the coping strategies illustrates the conducted adaptation of the teachers in the locale and ways of teaching. Adaptation played a crucial role as teachers adjusted their teaching methods based on the level of the students. They focused on the well-being of the IP learners, employed culturally relevant methods, and committed to learning the culture of the students to overcome the challenges. The following utterances may further describe this:

...medyo i level jud nimo gamay imong teaching, imong abilidad, imong medium of instruction sa mga bata kay lahi rajud ang mga bata sa bukid. – (IDI2)

You have to level your teaching, your ability, and medium of instruction towards the students because students in far-flung area are different.

...nag adjust pud ko sa ilahang culture kay lahi lahi jud baya mig culture nuh, so kailangan nako maging careful. – (IDI4)

I also adjust in their culture because we have different culture, so I have to be careful.

Adjustment... daghan man... in terms sa kuan... sa pag adapt sa ilahang culture, ug sa language pud... naga hinay hinay naman kog tuon. – (IDI5)

I have a lot of adjustments, in terms in adapting their culture and their language. I am slowly learning.

Language Learning of Teachers. This theme stemmed from the disclosed coping strategies of the participants focusing on their efforts to learn the IP language. Teachers dedicated themselves to learning the language of the learners. By learning and integrating the learners' language, teachers could adapt their communication style to better connect with and understand their learners. Also, this aimed to enhance their teaching-learning process. The following utterances can provide a further description:

...kato mag learn ko, maningkamot ko na maka learn sa ilahang kuan... dialect nila para ma explain nako ug tarong. – (IDI4)

I am working hard to learn their dialect for me to explain things clearly to them.

...nag learn ko... nag hinay hinay kog tuon sa ilahang language... and then, akoad pang gi immerse akoang self sa ilang culture. – (IDI5)

I am slowly learning their language and then I also immerse myself in their culture.

Learn their language jud. Bahalag ginagmay lang sa hantod makabalo na jud ka. – (FGD2)

Learn their language little by little until you can finally learn.

Magtuon jud sa ilahang language kay makatabang syag dako para mapadali ang imong pag communicate... – (FGD3)

Learning their language can help a lot in order for you to communicate easily.

...ang pag tuon sa ilang b'laan numbers para mas makasabot sila ug naka balo ko nga layo rajud kaayo ang ...sa bisaya or english word – (FGD4)

Learning their b'laan numbers for them to understand more and I also learned that the names of their ... english word.

...so kay lahi man ang pangalan sa mga number sa ilahang language, akoang gi learn to nga mga number para mas dali nila ma sabtan. – (FGD5)

Since the names of the number are different in their language, I learn how to say it using their language for them to understand easily.

Help-Seeking Behavior. This theme was drawn from the disclosed coping strategies of the participants, which involved seeking assistance from co-teachers of the same ethnicity as the learners or someone from the community. Teachers conducted home visits, used this opportunity to seek assistance from parents on language learning, and encouraged them to participate actively in their child's academic journey. Asking for help from those with more experiences and knowledge about the specific culture was the best approach for improvement. This can be further described by the following utterances:

...asking help from my co-teacher who is also a member of IP to translate some of the passages or words of the lessons. – (IDI3)

...sa mga parent jud ko kasagaran makakuha ug support... naga home visit man jud mi... magpa tudlo mi sa ilaha kung unsay b'laan sa kanang mga word... – (IDI4)

We seek support from the parents especially when we conduct home visitation, we asked them the translation of the words in their language.

...support from parents, nag patabang kog buhat ug mga... materials sa room nga pwede magamit sa klase. – (IDI5)

Support from parents, I asked them to help me make materials that I can use in my discussion.

Implementation of Peer-Learning. Peer learning played a significant role in enhancing communication and collaboration, especially in the participants' setting, where a language barrier exists between the teachers and their learners. Teachers assigned learners knowledgeable in the Bisaya language as the group leaders. These learners helped the teacher translate instructions and materials, which can improve the understanding and communication within the group. The following utterances may further describe this:

...butangan nako tog katong mga makasabot ug bisaya ang every group, so mao to sya ang murag mag silbing guide sa ilaha. – (IDI4)

I will assign students who can understand bisaya in every group, so they can stand as guide to their group.

...tagaan nimo silag lahi lahi nga mga activity para mas ilahang mas masabtan... kung kinsa tong mas makasabot ug bisaya himuon nimo tong leader. – (FGD3)

Give them different activities so that they can understand more. Make the student who can understand bisaya the leader of the group.

Implementation of Learner-Centered Instruction. Teachers integrated visual resources into their teaching strategies, which helped improve the educational process of the learners and enhanced their learning outcomes. This encouraged active involvement and collaboration among learners. The following utterances can further describe this theme:

Bali kanang dapat ang klase kay learner-centered sya, kanang naa jud silay involvement ba,...ana... bali kanang murag nalingaw pud sila ba while ga tuon... – (IDI4)

The class should be learner-centered, there should be involvement and cooperation of the students, something like they are having fun while learning.

Katong manipulatives jud ang effective... So para dali sya masabtan, tagaan nimo sila ug... manipulatives nga makita jud nila... – (IDI6)

Manipulatives are effective. You have to show them something or use manipulatives for them to understand easily.

...natagaan mig pinter sa una. Naa jud syay impact sa pagtudlo namo sa bata kay... maka show man mig picture sa ilaha para mas dali nila masabtan ang lesson... – (FGD1)

We received printer before and it really has an impact in teaching our learners because we can show them pictures related to the lesson so that they can easily understand.

...naga tudlo ka with visuals jud, mao na sya isa sa pinaka nindot nga method imong gamiton pag mag teach ka labi na sa elementary... – (FGD4)

Teaching with visuals is one of the most effective methods you can use especially in elementary.

The educators' coping strategies focused on their efforts to become more effective teachers for their IP learners. As illustrated, the findings emphasized the efforts of the participants to shape their pedagogy in pursuit of suitability to the students' language, which was crucial to their learning process. Also, the coping strategies revealed were focused on the students, especially with the learning materials. Also, one of the coping strategies involved the assistance of the individuals in the community, who were also part of the teachers' pursuit of learning the local language.

Shared Insights to the Academic Community

The shared insights revealed below were categorized and labeled based on the teachers' narratives gathered from the interview. Specifically, as shown in Table 3, the insights revealed are as follows: a passion for teaching, companionship, and personal and professional growth.

Table 3. *Shared Insights to the Academe and Community*

<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Passion for Teaching	Perseverance of teachers at IP-recognized schools Fostering respect and understanding of culture illustrated by IP learners Touching the lives of IP learners through education
Companionship	Building friendships in the community Opportunity to foster authentic connection with the IP community Mutual benefit among the teachers and the community
Personal and Professional Growth	Educating students as a medium for growth Leveraging the opportunity to teach for professional growth Developing persistence

Passion for Teaching. The perseverance of teachers in IP schools exemplified their dedication and commitment to delivering quality education in a challenging environment. They respected and integrated the cultural traditions, language, and values of the indigenous community they served. Despite the numerous obstacles, they remained committed and positive, ensuring their learners received the possible education. Their efforts played a crucial role in empowering indigenous learners. Their revealed utterances can further describe this theme:

...teaching is hard, it takes all your intellectual, social and emotional nuance and determination. Every day I ... I'm sharing my life with my pupils – (IDI3)

...dapat as teachers, we should love our work, and also ang pag teach sa mga IP learner, kay luoy baya sila, and ... tag materials nga relevant or meaningful sa ilaha. - (IDI5)

As a teacher, we should love our work, especially in teaching IP learners and then we should innovate materials that are relevant or meaningful to them.

...understand and respect the cultures and ways of living of the IP learners. Do not put them in your shoes but ... and build connection – (IDI7)

Companionship. Teachers who learned and embraced the culture of the community and shared knowledge and skills respectfully and integratively took essential steps toward building friendships and authentic connections. They immersed themselves in the culture to establish a deeper connection and understanding of the culture. This approach promoted mutual understanding and collaboration to achieve more meaningful development within the community. Also, the following utterance may provide further description:

... dapat buhaton nimo is ifriend nimo ang mga tao sa community, kay sila man gud ang isa sa mag tabang sa imoha... in terms sa dialect, sila pud maka tabang sa imoha... – (IDI4)

Make friends with the people in the community because they are the one who can help you, and in terms of the dialect, ... one who can help you.

...mas ma motivate ko nga mupadayon ug share sa akong knowledge... dili lang sa akoang students pati napud sa... ahmm... community. – (IDI5)

It motivates me to continue sharing my knowledge not only in my students but also to the community.

You have to build connection to them. It is called authentic teaching... authentic connections between the learners and the teachers. – (IDI7)

It helps a lot when it comes in teaching also in community maka build ka ug strong relationship... – (FGD7)

It helps a lot when it comes in teaching also in the community, you can build a strong relationship.

Personal and Professional Growth. The teachers who learned the language of the community not only supported communication but also enhanced their linguistic skills. In addition, the opportunity to make a positive impact on the lives of the IP learners and knowing that their efforts contributed to the learners' academic outcomes brought a deep sense of fulfillment to the teachers. Their experiences teaching in an IP community significantly contributed to their personal and professional growth. The utterances of the participants can further describe this theme:

Since I educate pupils about so much more than academic content, I educate them about the world. It has an impact ... a humble and professional one. – (IDI3)

Never let the challenges hinder your teaching profession for the IP students, keep going... – (FGD10)

The revealed themes presented various insights shared by the teachers teaching mathematics among IP-recognized schools. They mentioned that through their profession, they could keep their passion for teaching burning, since they witnessed the need for the community's students. Additionally, the experience in the community enabled them to put importance on the genuine relationships that

can be built regardless of being not a native and encountering challenges. Ultimately, the participants' experiences pushed them to be better educators and individuals.

Conclusions

Given the language differences, teaching in an IP-recognized school undeniably impacts teaching dynamics and the overall way of life. Language, being crucial for communication, affects lesson delivery, leading to a ripple effect on student-teacher relationships. Unfortunately, this gap can result in disrespect from students, including being laughed and whispered at. Despite these challenges, teachers continue their efforts, with some serving for up to 11 years.

This study aimed to understand teachers' experiences in similar settings to discover methods for improving learners' academic performance in IP-recognized schools and to help teachers refine their teaching methods to better align with the learning styles of IP students in mathematics. The study revealed various coping strategies used by participants, showing that while teachers seek help, they are also actively finding ways to overcome their challenges. Despite facing language barriers and feelings of alienation, participants worked to build relationships within the community to better understand and integrate with the local culture. They leveraged these connections to gather information that would benefit their students.

I resonate with the insights shared by the participants, reflecting their passion for teaching and the resilience they have developed. Despite the challenges, their commitment to educating individuals in need of education demonstrates their dedication to their profession. As they strive to assist their students, they grow as professionals and individuals. This study gave me a deeper understanding of my fellow teachers' experiences and valuable insights to enhance my teaching methods. Teaching in an IP-recognized school for over two years has been challenging, with many ups and downs, but it has strengthened my commitment and passion for teaching. I am deeply grateful for this experience, which has contributed significantly to my personal, emotional, and professional growth and will always hold a special place in my heart.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Ella Mae M. Lopez

Tribal Filipino School of Bilibak Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines